

Sales Promotion at Keshva Enterprise Bidar

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Abstract- India continues to have an encouraging industrial activity and the corresponding healthy demand from customers. Tractors' requirements are expected to grow substantially agricultural country. Greater productivity and great performance are the two main contributions in the mechanization of any country. Thus, the tractor plays an important role as an integral part of increasing agricultural productivity. The dealership for the John Dear Tractor is being done by Keshav Enterprise, Bidar for Bidar area. The executive summary of Keshav Enterprise, Bidar which is a sole proprietorship start in the year 2009.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sales promotion has become one of the many important sets for product service. The satisfaction survey is becoming the main tool for evaluating this aspect of customer service. The goal of the Deere and the company is to put quality for the product. Sales promotion plays an essential role in the relationship with the customer. The project is designed to provide an opportunity for students participating in the field experience. A project is 10 weeks and holds a position during the 4th semester of MBA. My internship theme is customer satisfaction with the John deer tractor at Keshav Enterprises Bidar. The size of the survey is in the city of Bidar to find out if Sales promotion or not with the John Deer tractor in the city. The customer's opinion can help identify how to improve the product.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

- Customer satisfaction:

Sales promotion is a marketing strategy where the product is promoted using short-term attractive initiatives to stimulate its demand and increase its sales.

This strategy is usually brought to use in the following cases –

- to introduce new products,

- sell out existing inventories,
- attract more customers, and
- to lift sales temporarily.

Satisfaction of customer is the thinking to show of the produce or the service of the single in relation to his expectations. The experience expectation of coincidence will be met. And whose expectations are exceeded will be very satisfied.

Sales promotion is a handy technique to fulfill the short term sales goals by persuading potential customers to buy the product. It is an important promotional strategy to –

Sales promotion is linked with customer behavior to fine different types of customers with fully satisfied and loyal consumers who continue to buy and pass on to other very positive information about the company. Who feel positive satisfied with equally to stop doing there business with the company and spread negative word of mouth. Dis satisfied consumers who stay with the company due to a individual or low cost environment and which are difficult and expensive by manage due to their frequent complaints.

The importance of Sales promotion to decreases when the was bargaining rights and customer satisfaction to expand there business to satisfied with services and products by providing the company. Sales promotion refers to the customer needs a product to meet their performance(perceived performance) and expectations (expectations) to compare the sentiment of the state. Sales promotion is a low level of complaint about the most common expression but he did not complain that he did not necessarily show that the customer was satisfied and employees of product and service companies directly for the overall assessment, business customers, products services and staff recognition. Customers based on their value judgment.

Accel Henry likewise trusts that the normal outcomes

from the real utilization of merchandise for the purchaser lead to palatable outcomes or regardless reason client disappointment.

As can be found in the past definition, the dimension of apparent fulfillment is the distinction between the capacity of impacts and desires. In the event that the outcomes are lower than anticipated, the client will be fulfilled if the apparent impacts and desires concur with client fulfillment. If more than the apparent impact of desire clients will be fulfilled or upbeat. When all is said in done consumer loyalty is straightforwardly spoken to by clients and workers of items and administrations organizations for the general appraisal of business client's item administrations and faculty acknowledgment. Clients dependent on their esteem decisions to assess items and administrations consumer loyalty client prerequisites have been met dependent on their dimension of involvement.

Sales promotion is a low level of complaint about the most common expression but did not complain that it did not necessarily prove that the customer was satisfied. Even if the customer specifies the requirements and satisfies the customer's wishes it does not necessarily guarantee that the customer is satisfied. Philip Kotler believes that customer satisfaction is a person in the perceived effects of a product with its expectations of forming a sense of pleasure or a state of disappointment. Accel Henry also believes that the expected results from the actual consumption of goods for the consumer lead to satisfactory results or in any case cause customer disappointment. As can be found in the past definition, the dimension of apparent fulfillment is the distinction between the capacity of impacts and desires. In the event that the outcomes are lower than anticipated the client will be fulfilled whenever saw impacts and desires match consumer loyalty. If more than the apparent impact of desires, clients will be fulfilled or glad. When all is said in done consumer loyalty is spoken to by client.

- STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The problem is studied is "SALES PROMOTION WITH JOHN DEERE TRACTOR AT BIDAR"

Need of the study:

- The need for the study is Sales promotion with the John Deere tractor and analysis of the customer's opinion on the John Deere tractor.
- Today's highly sophisticated life means that the marketing specialist knows the pulse of the market. If the company wants to survive in the competitive market, it must identify customer needs and try to reach them.
- The client's needs are dynamic, that's why he's looking for something new to meet their needs. This is why customer satisfaction has become a separate area of study.
- The study was conducted to determine Sales promotion with the John Deere tractor reference.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

- Know consumer loyalty with the different highlights and advances utilized.
- Identify the reason behind the purchase of the John Deere tractor.
- Analyze John Deere user preferences based on technology and price.
- Identify customer feedback on John Deere tractor service performance.
- Evaluate the performance of the John Deere tractor used by farmers.
- To find out if the performance of John Deere tractors matches the customer's expectations.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

- This study provides an overview of the John Deere tractor,
- This study shows how customers feel about the John Deere tractor service.
- The study takes into account the customers' opinion about the John Deere tractor.
- This study also helps John Deere tractor dealers get to know the buyer's experience at the time of the bumps and also helps the John Deere tractor manufacturer to learn about Sales promotion

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED:

Primary data is data that is accumulated for the first

time, also known as new data. Primary data accumulated by direct interaction with discouragement through questionnaires.

SOURCES OF PRIMARY DATA

The essential information is gathered by the respondents when the survey question is asked.

SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data collected from the official John Deere tractor web sites and data were collected from data available from sources

Design research	expressive
Source of data	Primary and secondary data
Do Research approach	review method
Do research instruments	questionnaires
review location	Bidar district
Sample size	50 customers

III. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

Table no 1:

Your age ranges from

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
21-30	09	18%
31-40	13	26%
41-50	22	44%
50- Others	06	12%
Total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

The diagram above demonstrates that 44% of clients

of John Deere tractors are somewhere in the range of 41 and 50 years of age and 26% are somewhere in the range of 31 and 40 years of age.

INTERPRETATION:

Most John Deere tractor customers are between 41 and 50 years old.

Table no 2:

Employment of respondents?

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
Former	48	96%
Business man	0	0%
Contractor	0	0%
Others	02	4%
Total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

Above, the chart shows that out of 50 respondents, 48 respondents are farmers and none of them are entrepreneurs or entrepreneur

INTERPRETATION:

The majority of John Deere tractor user occupation is agriculture (farmers)

Table no 3:

How did you get to know the John Deere tractor?

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
Advertisement	03	6%
Friends	07	14%
Relatives	01	02%
Others	39	78%
Total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

From the table above we can deduce that 78% of tractors come from it through other sources.

INTERPRETATION:

At least the respondents are in line with the John Deere tractor for advertisements and relatives and many of them through other sources.

Table no 4:

Which John Deere tractor model do you have?

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
50-50 EHP	7	14%
5310 EHP	25	50%
5390 EHP	8	16%
Others	10	20%
Total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

50% of respondents use 5310 and 18% of respondents use a 5390 hp tractor.

INTERPRETATION: Here, 50 of the studio's customers use multiple model 5310 E-HP tractors, i.e., these model

tractors.

Table no 5

How many years have you used the John Deere tractor?

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
2years	14	28%
4 years	25	50%
6 years	5	10%
More than 6 years	6	12%
Total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

50% of them said that the John Deere tractor has been using it for 4 years and 10% of those interviewed used it for 6 years.

INTERPRETATION:

Most respondents use John Deere tractors for 4 years.

Table no 6:

What are you using the tractor for?

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
Agriculture	41	82%
Transportation	6	12%
Drilling	1	2%
other purpose	2	4%
Total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

From the table above, it is clear that 82% of John Deere's customers use agricultural tractors, 12% for transport, 2% for drilling and 4% for other purposes.

INTERPRETATION:

More respondents bought the John Deere tractor for agricultural purposes.

Table no 7:

Are you satisfied with the John Deere tractor price?

Particular	Respondent	% Percentage
Yes	50	100%
No	0	0%
Total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

100% of respondents are very satisfied with the price of John Deere tractors; There is nobody who is not satisfied with its price.

INTERPRETATION:

All customers are satisfied with the John Deere tractor price.

Table no 8:

What is your opinion about the mileage of the John Deere tractor?

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
Excellent	33	66%
Good	12	24%
can't say	2	4%
Poor	3	6%
Total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

The graph above shows that 66% of respondents rated John Deere excellent and 24% good.

INTERPRETATION

Most customers are very satisfied with their mileage.

Table no 9:

What do you think of the maintenance of the John Deere tractor?

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
very less	9	18%
Less	27	54%
Very high	00	00%
High	14	28%

ANALYSIS:

In the table above, it is clear that 54% of customers have a good opinion in track maintenance or John Deere.

INTERPRETATION;

Most respondents said that John Deere tractors have less maintenance.

Table no 10

Have you satisfied by the service provider in the showroom (service center)

Particular	Respondents	Percentage
Highly satisfied	30	60%
just satisfied	13	26%
Dissatisfied	2	4%
highly Dissatisfied	5	10%
total	50	100%

ANALYSIS:

From the table above we can deduce that a respondent is satisfied with the service offered by the John Deere tractor, 60% of the customers are highly qualified and 26% of the customers are satisfied.

INTERPRETATION:

About 60% of respondents are very satisfied with John Deere's services.

IV. FINDINGS

- Many customers in the Bidar district use the John Deere 5310 E-HP model tractor.
- More than respondents use the John Deere tractor for agricultural purposes.
- Respondents are with the John Deere tractor price

V. SUGGESTIONS

- Improve services and quality management, as still few customers are not satisfied.
- Adopt new strategies to gain brand awareness in the market.
- To produce more powerful tractor engines.

CONCLUSION

The analysis part of the survey shows that the Bidar district is a large potential market for the John Deere tractor. Most customers use a John Deere tractor for its new features, good mileage and quality. Note that multiple John Deere tractors are used by farmers for agricultural purposes. The company should expand more showrooms and focus on ads and other promotional activities. In the end I conclude that John Deere Company must identify the needs and needs of the client and try to achieve it.

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